

An integrated method for the
Hybrid assessment of the **I**mpacts and **B**enefits of
the nature-based **sO**lutions in **U**rban system

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HIBOU
Integrated method
for the
Hybrid
assessment of the
Impacts and
Benefits
of the nature-
based **sO**lutions
in **U**rban systems

Assess the **efficiency** of the **Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)** for **urban** projects, based on an **integrated** approach, by considering:

- their **benefits** (e.g. for summer heat or stormwater management, for biodiversity, etc.)
&
- their **impacts** (e.g. on water consumption, on carbone emissions, etc.)
versus or in synergy with
theirs **alternatives** (e.g. air conditioning, stormwater harvesting, etc.)

to adress the various **urban challenges**

- 1) the interactions (benefits & impacts) between the NBS and the urban project take place:
 - on the project site (*in situ*), but also
 - at the global scale (*ex-situ*)
- 2) the **multifunctionality** (i.e. provide multiple benefits simultaneously) of the NBS should be considered in the results analysis of impacts ;
- 3) the **integrated** approach implies:
 - a **common macro-model** for characterizing the system to be assessed;
 - **shared semantics and ontology across** different areas of expertise (biodiversity, hydrology, etc.);
 - the **interdependence** of the results for each adressed challenge.

A set of quantitative and qualitative **indicators**, based on the **hybridization** of various scientific methods, according to the **integrated approach** principles (shared semantics and ontology, common macro-model, and results interdependence)

The present version of the HIBOU method & associated toolset allow to **assess the urban projects contribution to:**

✓ the **climate change** impact (1 indicator);

✓ the **biodiversity** *in situ* and *ex situ*, by using a family of 9 indicators to cover as much as possible the five pressures on the biodiversity (global warming, land use change, pollution, overexploitation of resources, introduction of invasive species);

✓ the **stormwater management** (2 indicators);

✓ the **urban heat island (UHI)** effect and mitigation strategies (1 to 3 indicators);

✓ the **urban quality for the citizens**, based on a qualitative assessment grid considering 24 criteria.

Collaborative approach to meet the final goal of the HIBOU method:

contribute to the **definition of the pathways**

to **reach the targets** in addressing the various **urban challenges** through the identification and promotion of the **most suitable solutions in each context**

For each indicator:

➤ **Absolute value**

➤ **Normalized value**

% of the max. potential at the time of the study and considering the local constraints of each project

e.g. for the in-situ Biodiversity (indicator : harmonized Biotype Area Factor (0-1), BAFh), if the maximum BAFh of the project site is 0.6 and the BAFh for the designed project is 0.48, then the project reaches 80% of the maximum potential.

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50%
SMEs and Industries

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Assessment of an urban project, considering the NBS and other interventions: the renovation actions for the existing buildings, the new buildings construction, the landscaping of outdoor spaces

Environmental footprint

Climate change

Ex - situ Biodiversity

Kg eq CO2 /m²

PDF.m².an
PDF : Potentially
Disappeared
Fraction of species

Risk management Urban Heat Island (UHI)

ΔT °C

Simulated temperature difference between the project site in urban area and its surrounding rural areas

In situ Biodiversity Land use change and occupation

BAFh: Harmonized Biotpe Area Factor (0-1)

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Present site

Designed alternatives

Final project

Input data

ADDRESS	
Address	
Owner/Type of ownership	
Year of construction	
Building state (new, renovated). If renovated, list the year of renovation and the main applied interventions	
Energy Performance (e.g. n20, class A, B, C)	
Building type: residential, office, educational, healthcare, commercial, industrial	
Brief description (e.g. apartment blocks)	
BUILDING DATA	
Number	Green space's name
Number	Surface (m ²)
Total m ²	Availability of technical drawings
Type of	Open ground or on slab
	If the "on slab": soil thickness
	Soil type
	Soil properties
	Soil specific heat (MJ/g.K)
	Soil porosity (dimensionless)
	Soil conductivity (W / m.K)
	Green spaces on the ground
	Vegetation type (m ²)
	Irrigation schedules (cm/week)
	Sedum
	Crop
	Short grass
	Tall grass
	Evergreen shrub
	Deciduous shrub
	Evergreen tree
	Deciduous tree
	I do not know
	Presence of poplar and/or cedar

Modelling and simulation based on the integrated method

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111354>

Output data

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Thank you for your attention!

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WILSON: Distributed data modelling and federated digital tWInning for Lifecycle data driven Sustainable Operation and management of buildiNgS and districts

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